

Evidence-based development of inclusive schools – a review of European research

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ABSTRACT

On the legal- and educational politics levels, a decisive prerequisite for inclusive education has been initiated by the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, which has been ratified by many countries. When schools are approaching the overarching goal of providing optimal support for all learners, evidence-based research is needed to support teachers, school principals, school administrators, school inspectors, external consultants, pupils, parents and education policymakers. Within their specific view of school, they provide education in a reasonably targeted way. In the frame of a multifaceted scientific exchange, international experts aimed to bridge the evidence gap by providing and sharing insight into their work within inclusion. The intense exchange of knowledge and discussion on different theories and empirical data led to improved knowledge of participants as well as to a shared view on evidence-based development of inclusive schools in different national contexts. This research review discusses about evidence-based development of inclusive schools at different levels of actors; in addition, perspectives and initiatives for further research will be given.

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Introduction

This review focuses on the evidence-based development of inclusive schools based on a multifaceted scientific exchange (SE) held in Zurich in October 2023. With a common goal towards inclusive education, the discussion brought together international experts to explore structural, pedagogical and governance-related factors influencing evidence-based development of inclusive schools in different countries. Our aim is to identify, assess and develop systems that ensure quality education for all students. As a topic, evidence-based development of inclusive schools is relevant and important; we will give theoretical as well as practical insights and bridge research findings across different levels of (educational) systems.

The 2015 Incheon Declaration of the World Forum on Education declared inclusion and equity as fundamental preconditions for quality education. The United Nations' Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (UNCRPD) of 2006 insists on the obligation of educational institutions to provide an individualised response to individual needs. On the legal- and educational politics levels, a decisive prerequisite for inclusive education has been initiated. Special needs education (SNE) services are defined in the regulatory frameworks of the countries and regions. School authorities and school administrators, together with teachers, implement the services locally in a variety of ways.

The conditions for success of inclusive school in a multilevel system have been investigated and defined in international studies (e.g. Ainscow and Booth 2017; Preuss 2018; Wirtz 2020). Whether at the discursive or educational policy level, at the administrative, institutional, principal or teacher level, measures can be taken to strengthen inclusive schools. The development of an inclusive school differs from general school development because specific elements need to be considered.

Up to now, neither literature nor concepts on evidence-based development of inclusive schools exist. The SE: 'Evidence-based development of inclusive schools' aimed to present the latest research results and discuss their insights constructively. The SE took place from 17 to 19 October 2023 in Zurich, Switzerland. More than 70 participants from Switzerland, Germany and Austria took part. Roundtable discussions followed every three or four presentations. The exchange ended with a workshop. The SE managed to synthesise empirical findings and theoretical approaches, and Rolff's (2016) three-level school development model was used as a theoretical framework.

Rolff (2016) distinguishes organisational, personnel and teaching development with regard to school development processes. The model is based on organisational development as the starting point for school development. The area of personnel development comprises the area of staff development that 'includes staff training, staff management and staff personnel development' (Rolff 2016, 33), while teaching development comprises components such as methodology, subject didactics and social learning. Control processes at the macro level (e.g. education policy) play a role in the model insofar as they determine the framework conditions for the development of individual schools (Rolff 2016).

Literature shows that education systems are complex and often not controlled hierarchically. System theories (Luhmann 1984), neo-institutionalism (Mejer and Rowan 1977), educational governance (Kussau and Brüsemeister 2007) or actor-network-

theory (Latour 2007) can broaden their view of the processes of coordinating the actions of actors in different systems. Neo-institutionalist approaches used to observe change and governance processes in schools (e.g. Pfänder et al. 2018), explain the practices of organisations not in terms of efficacy and efficiency, but in terms of legitimacy. Cultural beliefs and rules often structure cognitive assumptions and guide decision-making.

Accountability, quality control and quality assurance in schools and teaching are other perspectives to look at school development. The model for educational and school quality of Ditton (2017) is widely accepted. The interrelationships between teaching and school operations are regarded as the core area for ensuring school quality. The effects achieved are, on the one hand, to the intentions that are to be pursued. In addition, the structural, financial, material and personnel conditions must be reflected. Regarding the effects achieved with the students, a distinction is made between short-term and long-term effects. The quality of teaching refers to the relation between teachers and students, the quality of the teaching content and materials used as well as the quality of teaching and learning. Aspects of school quality relate to the four overarching areas of school culture, school management, cooperation and coordination, and staff development.

Wirtz (2020) analysed which qualitative components play a role in the transformation of the education system towards inclusion and what significance they can have for the (further) development of inclusive educational programs. She found that allocation of resources, school- and teacher-leadership, cooperation and teaching and didactics are significant factors to promote learning outcomes for all children.

Inclusion is a transformational scope (Koenig 2022) and people should be aware not to simplify things too much. Governance of educational systems, as well as that of the organisation of the individual school, is a difficult and risky business (Kruschel and Merz-Atalik 2023, 5). An awareness of the complex interrelated factors that compeded inclusion and the question of what really happens in school and which knowledge is needed at school, are central issues to start with. Based on findings in qualitative (ethnographical) research on individualised and personalised teaching and learning and inclusive schools, interdependences between continuing orders of difference and discrimination within and outside of school can be found. Reforms are accompanied by contradictory effects, and school development processes often are contingent (Rabenstein, Gnauck, and Schäffer 2019).

Ensuring that students receive effective instruction and support is of great importance, and we cannot support a claim of inclusion without evidence. Unfortunately, there are little empirical data to support full inclusion for all students. The theories which are leading evidence-based research on inclusion are different and need different levels of action to measure outcomes. Research done systematically and professionally leads to evidence, inductive and deductive approaches are complementary. Studies can be categorised in different systematic manners, e.g. to levels of generalisability (Knigge 2020). These can be ethnographic studies as well as other qualitative or quantitative studies.

This review aims to identify and assess evidence-based quality aspects of inclusive schools divided into (1) system development, (2) organisational development, (3) personnel and child development and (4) teaching development, and chapters following the theoretical framework which was used in SE.

System development

The chapter on system development explores how inclusive education is shaped by governance structures, accountability systems and resource allocation. Using participatory multilevel network analysis (PMNA), it was shown that educational change is not a linear top-down process but a negotiated adaptation involving actors at multiple levels. Inclusive school development benefits from whole system approaches with shared visions and feedback loops. However, current accountability tools such as large-scale assessments (LSA) often exclude students with special educational needs (SEN), limiting their relevance for inclusive practices. Funding models also play a key role: systems with throughput funding allow more flexibility and inclusion than those with input-based allocation. Preliminary findings from Swiss cantons reveal varying professional profiles among special educators, with implications for effective resource use. The chapter highlights the need for inclusive assessment methods, better data on resource allocation and governance strategies that support equity in education.

Participatory multilevel network analysis

The analytic instrument of educational governance focuses on steering mechanisms and impulses that are offered by various actors at different levels in the multilevel actor system, often undermined by heterogeneous or divergent interests. Transformation is not to be understood as a linear top-down process of implementation and schools do not simply adopt prepared solutions or concepts of research, politics or administrations (Merz-Atalik and Beck 2020). Rather, they try to carefully adapt new approaches for their own school situation and adjust them compatibly to their specific organisational conditions (Altrichter and Feyerer 2012; Altrichter and Maag Merki 2010; Kussau and Brüsemeister 2007). Within educational governance, education systems operate at national, regional and local levels (vertical interaction). Within them, schools function as distinct organisations and connect to each other or other types of organisations (horizontal interaction). Each education system can be characterised by its specific composition: by the policy instruments and measures used, and by the distribution of power and interaction of actors across different levels (Altrichter and Maag Merki 2010; Kussau and Brüsemeister 2007). Within education systems, the subsystems are loosely coupled (Weick 2009). To analyse coordination of actions between different levels and actors, Merz-Atalik and Beck (2023) used participatory multilevel network analysis in several countries to reflect on experiences on the implementation of inclusive schools. Their result confirm that participative and whole system approaches in the change management with continuous feedback loops, based on a strong shared vision, can support a development towards more inclusive education systems (Merz-Atalik 2025; Merz-Atalik and Beck 2023).

Accountability

Large-scale assessments, comparative educational surveys, are widely used to inform policy on the quality and effectiveness of educational systems. Large-scale assessments provide an output-oriented perspective on the education system, and they are relevant for actors of education policy and educational research as they measure competencies

by performance tests. The methodological design of LSA is designed to measure the performance of educational systems and to compare groups of students stratified by the standardised sampling processes. Therefore, the data of LSA are reported on international, national or regional level and cannot be used by schools directly for school development (Fickermann and Maritzen 2014). LSA compare skills, knowledge, attitudes and behaviours across different populations and subpopulations of interest. In international LSA, the internationally standardised sampling procedure describes what proportion of pupils in the target population may be excluded from the test. In PISA (Program for International Student Assessment), each participating country can exclude a maximum of 5% of the target population if required and approved by the international consortium (OECD 2023). The exclusion of schools or pupils follows the sampling procedure. In the two-stage, stratified sampling procedure for PISA, a school sample is first drawn. In Switzerland, special education schools and schools that do not teach in one of the Swiss national languages are excluded from school sampling (Verner, Erzinger, and Fässler 2019). This is followed by sampling at the pupil level in the sampled schools. In a second step, the students are sampled in the selected schools. The school then assesses the test-taking ability of each selected student. The first step is to identify any SEN the student may have and then to assess whether the student is able to complete the tests and questionnaires 'independently and without assistance'. If the school deems a student ineligible, he or she will be excluded from PISA. The exclusion of students from the survey means that LSA data are even less meaningful for the analysis of students with SEN and of inclusive schools. To overcome these barriers, PISA offers countries a short version of the test. In addition, the test results are not comparable between the standard forms and the short forms, which makes them difficult to interpret (OECD 2023).

The current use of the term special educational needs (SEN) in PISA, which refers to the decision to exclude special education schools and individual students with SEN from participation in the school achievement assessment due to the lack of test-taking ability, is questionable. However, to standardise the exclusions from LSA between the schools as much as possible, such criteria are valuable. This is also where the greatest challenge lies when it comes to ensuring that all students in a school are included in LSA. The standardisation of sampling and administration procedures across countries requires concrete criteria that can be applied in a comparable manner so that the results are comparable.

To overcome these barriers, it is necessary to create theoretical foundations and clarify terminology so that inclusive settings can be considered in LSA. For example, it is possible to oversample certain subpopulations to be able to interpret the results appropriately (Erzinger 2025). And especially regarding school development processes (not only in inclusive schools), it is important to bear in mind that, due to their methodological design, LSA data are used to describe results rather than to explain them. LSA can represent a starting point for system and school development processes.

Resource allocation

Wicki and Antognini (2022) showed that the regulatory framework has an effect on the level and manner of SNE, separation and inclusion rates (Wicki and Antognini 2022). International studies show that, in education systems with low segregation rates, more

resources are throughput-funded than in systems with high segregation rates. With throughput funding, schools are more flexible in allocating the resources where needed. With resources allocated individually to students with SEN (input-funding) it is less flexibility. With throughput funding, it is important to find out whether students with SEN receive enough and proper resources. More assessments of learning abilities and capabilities will be necessary (e.g. Banks, Frawley, and McCoy 2015).

Basically, it is evident at the institutional level of inclusive schools that a flexible use of resources within the school, which is oriented to needs, is 'extremely preconditioned' (IfBQ 2016, 52). Further, inclusion-related cooperation only becomes effective when it is based on specific competencies and inclusion-related know-how. But to answer the question, how many resources do schools have for SNE and how these resources are allocated within the concrete school or classroom, data and evidence-based results are still lacking. A questionnaire has been developed to assess the amount, type and allocation of resources for SNE at regular schools. The questionnaire has been used in five cantons. A useful nationally and internationally comparable indicator for measuring resources for special support is the number of pupils per special educator (Wicki 2025). To analyse how special educators use their resources, it is possible to ask about the division of working time into operational activities (teaching in the classroom or separately), support activities (such as supervising pupils, teachers, parents and cooperating with other specialists) and work in the technical structure (e.g. diagnostics in and outside of assessment procedures). With cluster analysis, professional work profiles of special educators have been identified (Wicki and Rauber 2024). Next steps will be to analyse the effects of the quantity of resources, resource allocation and work profiles of special educators on school quality and segregation.

School and organisational development

Following the model of school quality (Ditton 2017), aspects of school quality relate to the areas of school culture, school management, cooperation and coordination, and staff development. But how these aspects can be assessed and developed? At the SE, Gebhardt presented the development of a short questionnaire to assess school quality highlighting its multilevel approach from individual needs to external support. In addition, Carpelan presented research results on the role of school leadership, which has pivotal role in developing inclusive education. Together, these insights underscore the necessity of coherent, evidence-based approaches at all levels to advance inclusive schooling aligned with the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities.

Assessment of school quality

Based on the bioecological theory of human development (Bronfenbrenner 1980) and the Index for Inclusion (Ainscow and Booth 2017), the QU!S Questionnaire has been developed to assess school quality (Heimlich 2018). The starting hypothesis for the development of QU!S was the assumption that inclusive school development entails changes at several levels of schools. (1) The level of children and young people with individual needs, and (2) the level of teaching and inclusive education; (3) the level of multiprofessional cooperation in the team; (4) the level of the inclusive school concept and school life;

and (5) the level of the external support system and networking with the environment (Heimlich 2018). The Questionnaire contains 125 questions for self-evaluation of schools. A valid and reliable shortened version was developed as an open resource and supports school boards, school leaders and teachers to assess school quality (Schurig et al. 2020).

The QUIS Questionnaire, as well as comparable instruments for school development, has been developed for internal school development, but so far they are not connected to external quality securing instruments, such as school inspection, so further development in connecting those two strategies is needed. Beforehand, a consensus building and intention setting as to what quality in inclusive education or what a qualitative inclusive school looks like will be necessary. Such an ‘evidence-based instrument’ could inform policy-making and educational governance processes to reinforce national strategies in implementing the UNCRPD (Schurig 2025).

The importance of school leadership

School leaders have an important role in evidence-based development of inclusive schools. Carpelan and Lahtero (2025) examine the question of what contradictions and opportunities school administrators and teachers describe when they think about strengthening inclusive practices in schools. Research findings show that teachers want clear guidance from school leaders on what inclusion should be. School principals are often perceived as distant, meaning that they know little about the actual work of teachers. Thus, the development of the quality of teaching can be difficult (Eisenschmidt et al. 2025; Lahtero, Ahtiainen, and Lång 2019). Ahtiainen also poses questions concerning the content and structure of educational leadership training. She emphasises that principals need to have clear guidelines. Education policy sets the direction and the framework. This requires a strong will and understanding of the requirements for implementing inclusion at all levels of the education system (Carpelan and Lahtero 2025).

Evidence-based practices as part of normal teaching should be implemented in manageable chunks (Savolainen 2023). Teachers, parents, and pupils have to know school’s values and what they mean in practice. Setting a few but clear behavioural expectations that are taught progressively, positive feedback to reinforce good behaviour, and clear procedures for dealing with undesirable behaviour are key factors (Yada and Savolainen 2023; Schwab, Lindner, and Savolainen 2022).

Personnel and child development and development of teaching and didactics

This chapter gives a content-rich overview of four essential aspects of inclusive education practices: collaboration, quality of classroom interactions, cooperative lesson development and assessment of learning progress. Drawing on international research and practical models, it highlights how collaborative practices among educators, supported by reflective communication and a cultural-historical framework, can enhance inclusive processes (Paju et al. 2018, 2022; Paju 2025). The SURE intervention study demonstrates how targeted, video-based professional development can improve the quality of teacher–student interactions, with particular benefits for students with SEN (Altmeyer,

Antognini, and Eberli 2025). Involving students in lesson planning through the Inclusive Inquiry approach (Messiou and Ainscow 2020), Barbara Gasteiger-Klicpera's project illustrates how cooperative lesson development fosters mutual learning and responsibility among teachers and pupils across diverse European contexts. Finally, longitudinal research and tools such as the Levumi platform (Gebhardt and Ebenbeck 2025) emphasise the importance of early identification, progress monitoring and evidence-based assessments to guide pedagogical decisions and support the academic and socio-emotional development of all learners, particularly those with learning difficulties (Buchwald et al. 2022; Törmänen and Roebbers 2018). Together, these studies underscore the need for systemic, research-informed approaches to advance inclusive education.

Collaboration

Paju et al. (2022) showed that collaborative practices can support inclusive processes. Paju works as a special educator and principal in Finland and has developed a model for developing collaborative practices that focuses on reflective communication. Thorough analysis based on a cultural-historical perspective (e.g. Vygotsky 1978), it is possible to understand the underlying factors associated with perceived tensions and to evaluate established teaching practices. With the help of the staff's goal-oriented collaboration, separate views can be connected (Paju et al. 2018, 2022; Paju 2025).

Quality of classroom interactions

The quality of interactions of teachers and pupils is central to the academic and social development of pupils (Hamre et al. 2013). Through the intervention study 'Increasing the quality of classroom interactions in inclusive mainstream classes (SURE)', class teachers and special educators receive video-based further training with the aim of jointly enhancing the quality of classroom interactions. This ongoing longitudinal randomised control group study investigates how the quality of classroom interactions changes as a result of the respective further training, and whether these changes have a positive effect on school performance, perception of inclusion and behaviour in the classroom as well as on relationships with peers. Of particular interest is the question whether students with SEN benefit in a specific way from classroom development. The study involved 64 mainstream classes at primary school grades 3–6 from 14 cantons in German-speaking Switzerland (Altmeyer, Antognini, and Eberli 2021). Data quality and the comparability of the groups promise exciting results on the coaching effect with regard to increasing the quality of teaching interactions in inclusive lessons (Altmeyer, Antognini, and Eberli 2025).

Cooperative lesson development

Teaching quality can also be developed in collaboration with the pupils. Gasteiger-Klicpera used the Inclusive Inquiry concept, developed by Messiou and Ainscow (2020). The Inclusive Inquiry requires teachers to enter dialogues with students and with their peers about how to develop lessons that respond positively to learners' differences. Central to the strategy is the involvement of students as researchers, gathering information from

their classmates to assist in processes of lesson planning (Messiou and Ainscow 2020). It is a model of lesson-centred in-service training in schools. A cooperative lesson development and reflection of three teachers (so-called teacher trio) and their students takes place, based on planning, observing and analysing the researched lessons. The project of Gasteiger-Klicpera involved two cycles of collaborative action research carried out by teams of teachers and researchers in five primary schools, in cities from five countries (Graz, Southampton, Lisbon, Faro and Aarhus). Teachers as well as students could benefit: Teachers' reflection has been evaluated as their own practices have been questioned. The received feedback and appreciation were beneficial for them. Students expressed that experienced teachers work more, they learned about different learning needs and to assume responsibility for one's own learning (Gasteiger-Klicpera 2025).

Assessment of learning progress

The importance of proper measurements and educators' broad knowledge of children's special needs and developmental milestones was emphasised in Törmänen and Roebers' longitudinal study (2018). The study compared developmental outcomes of children having SEN in SNE classes and regular classes at a play-oriented kindergarten and after 2 years of schooling. Before school start, no differences in executive functions (EF) were found between the groups. However, children assigned to SNE had poorer language, fine motor skills, lower pre-academic self-concept, self-regulatory skills and social integration. After 2 years of schooling, the SNE and regular class groups differed significantly in academic achievements, EF, fine motor skills and cognitive self-regulatory skills. However, there were no differences except regarding their academic self-concept and social integration in favour for SNE classes. The study concluded that children with SEN in SNE did not experience similar cognitive and academic development as their peers in regular classes. The results highlight the need for analytic evaluation to define children with SEN, covering both cognitive processes and behavioural evaluations. Early identification has been a major issue in educational research targeting early interventions and which can also serve as a practical tool for inclusive education (Törmänen 2025).

Inclusive education requires an individual benchmark in assessment and a focus on progression in learning for all pupils, especially children with learning difficulties, so that teachers can adapt their support and teaching. Progress monitoring in the form of short, simple tests provides an economical and low-threshold way to collect quantitative and qualitative data on learning or behavioural progress. To make this particularly easy and free of charge, the online platform Levumi was founded in 2015 and enables the use of computer-based screenings, exercises, and progress monitoring tests in mathematics, reading and spelling as well as behaviour for all children, especially children with learning difficulties (Mühling, Jungjohann, and Gebhardt 2019). The idea is that teachers will gain an insight into students' learning progressions in the areas of reading, mathematics and behaviour. The results of learning trajectory diagnostics provide the basis for pedagogical decisions for support and are also feedback on the effectiveness of current teaching and pedagogical action (Blumenthal et al. 2022; Buchwald et al. 2022). Open research questions around progress monitoring are the use in practice and the training of teachers in order to use the tools as effectively as possible (Gebhardt and Ebenbeck 2025).

Discussion

The different content and discussion points of the SE were introduced with the following perspectives. Based on findings in qualitative (ethnographical) research on individualised and personalised teaching and learning and inclusive schools, interdependences between continuing orders of difference and discrimination within and outside of school can be found. Furthermore, it can be assumed that reforms are accompanied by contradictory effects, and school development processes often are contingent (Rabenstein, Gnauck, and Schäffer 2019). Thus, inclusive school development processes implicate a permanent reflection and debate about (non-)discriminating effects of learning and teaching for all school members. Researchers as well as school administrators, principals and teachers are asked to critically investigate widespread assumptions concerning school reforms by focusing if the reforms lead to the anticipated effect: e.g. they can question the assumptions, that learners benefit when differences in education are not thematised by category and instead think together with learners about ways of dealing with differences in an anti-discriminating way. Against the background of pedagogical action as a social process on one side Löser and Rabenstein (2025) point to exclusion processes in formally inclusive settings and uncover the difference-setting and discriminating factors which are still present in the school context and on the other side they underline the need of permanent reflection and debate about the efforts of inclusive education can do (Löser and Rabenstein 2025).

Oliver Koenig added in 2023: If educational policy increasingly encourages teacher education to become evidence-based, a gap will emerge between research knowledge and teaching practice (Koenig 2023; Wieser 2018). Evidence-based approaches often simplify the intricate dynamics of real-world phenomena. Furthermore, values are foundational for educational practices. Without an established aim or purpose, evidence-based approaches lack direction (e.g. Biesta 2010).

The presentations at SE in Zurich identified various actors which use the many opportunities to exert influence on system-, school- or staff development and development of instruction and didactics. Even if system- and school governance is a risky business, the importance of evidence was eminent. The theories which are leading evidence-based research on inclusion are different and need different levels of action to measure outcomes. All research done systematically and professionally leads to evidence, inductive and deductive approaches are complementary.

For the development of inclusive systems and schools, knowledge on good governance of inclusion is important. Weak collaboration and coordination can hinder the implementation of inclusion and can be detected with actor-network-mapping (Merz-Atalik and Beck 2023). A roundtable of all levels for the development of a 'we' is useful. Research also shows that not culture, but structures are a main factor in determining inclusion. New norms have to be implemented in structures to become effective (Dietze et al. 2020; Moser 2020; Moser and Egger 2017), and the regulatory framework, as well as the allocation of resources, has to be based on evidence, assessed by international and intranational comparable indicators (Wicki 2025; Wicki and Antognini 2022). With a clearly defined school quality assessment (e.g. the QU!S Questionnaire; Schurig et al. 2020) factors for school development towards inclusion can be identified. Interesting research projects are conducted to develop participative inclusive teaching to

reach all students (Gasteiger-Klicpera 2025), and high quality instructional support and cooperation between teachers (Altmeyer, Antognini, and Eberli 2021; Altmeyer, Antognini, and Eberli 2025). Short and practical screening methods to focus on the individual learning and to enhance the learning outcomes are developed to overcome long diagnostic processes (Buchwald et al. 2022). Leadership (Paju et al. 2018) as well as teachers feeling and reflective communications can be learned and further, solve problems (Eisenschmidt et al. 2025).

Implications (for further research)

Numerous research results were presented and discussed at the SE. Nevertheless, there are also different kinds of research gaps.

- (1) Evidence gap: results from studies allow for conclusions in thrown right but are contradictory when examined from a more abstract point of view.
- (2) Practical-knowledge gap: professional behaviour or practice deviates from research findings or is not covered by research.
- (3) Methodological gap: a variation of research methods is necessary to generate new insights or to avoid distorted findings.
- (4) Empirical gap: research findings or propositions need to be evaluated or empirically verified.
- (5) Population gap: research regarding the populations that are not adequately represented or under-researched in the evidence base or prior research.

Few examples for further research questions could be the following: (1) How can other resources, such as collaboration with parents and the work of multiprofessional teams, be better utilised? (2) How can parental and community involvement in inclusive education be explored? (3) Concerning the organisational level of educational system, which management processes support the development of inclusive schools at the various levels? and (4) How is leadership training on school inclusion affecting the outcomes?

Naturally, all these aspects emphasise the importance and the role of teacher education. Following the SE in Zurich participants will enhance collaboration and will constructively find out more about evidence-based development of inclusive schools.

Conclusion

The SE and this review highlight the multidimensional nature of developing inclusive schools. It was recognised that inclusive school reform is inherently contingent and complex. Evidence-based practices must be contextually grounded, collaborative and continuously reflective. Structural barriers – not cultural attitudes – are often the primary obstacles to inclusion. Thus, inclusion must be embedded in policy, resourcing frameworks, and institutional norms, not just pedagogical intentions. Thus, as inclusion transforms both systems and classrooms, a cross-disciplinary, multilevel approach is essential to sustain equitable, quality education for all (Wicki and Törmänen 2025).

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